

PROBONO

D9.7 PROBONO Standardization (I)

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DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

³ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social cobenefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardized framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001/2018/2001

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AFNOR	Association Française de Normalisation (French Standardization Association)
ANSI	American National Standards Institute
ASME	American Society of Mechanical Engineers
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Material
BIM	Building Information Management
BSI	British Standards Institution, Federal Office for Information Security
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CEN-CLC/JTC	CEN-CENELEC Joint Technical Committee
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DIN	German Institute for Standardization
DKE	German Commission for Electrotechnical, Electronic, and Information Technologies of DIN and VDE
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
EN standard	European standard
ESI	Electronic Signatures and Infrastructures
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
GBN	Green Building Neighbourhood
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICS	International Classification for Standards

Acronym	Description
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
IWA	International Workshop Agreement
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
LCA	Life-cycle assessment
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NSAI	National Standards Authority of Ireland
NSB	National Standardization Body
R&I	Research and Innovation
SC	Subcommittee
SDO	Standards Developing Organization
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
UK	United Kingdom
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardization
US	United States
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The present deliverable D9.7 provides an overview of the first results of Task 9.4 – *Standardization activities*, which goes on for the entire duration of the project. Within this deliverable, subtask ST9.4.1 – *Investigate relevant standards* is covered in particular. This document provides a general summary of the basic knowledge on standardization in order to bring the consortium on a uniform level in this respect. Nevertheless, the focus of this deliverable is on the standardization landscape, which is relevant to the PROBONO project and therefore also other related initiatives.

In a first step, the methodology of the standards research conducted is described. With essential keywords provided by the consortium and pre-defined areas, a search for standards with a strong link to PROBONO and consequently GBN was conducted. Mainly international and European standards were included in the standards overview and shared with the project partners in form of a dashboard. Besides providing a summary on relevant aspects regarding project related standards, the dashboard allows the consortium members to search for specific standards by using keywords. Altogether 482 standards were included in this overview.

The dashboard was also used within this deliverable to provide an overview of the standardization landscape related to PROBONO. The different technical committees on international and European level, which are responsible for the development of the standards are described. Special focus was put on the international technical committee (TC) on *Sustainable cities and communities* (ISO/TC 268) since the work within this committee can provide a basis to define the GBN framework of PROBONO. For particularly relevant topic areas related to PROBONO, possible relevant standards and TC's on European and international level are described.

All this information about standardization, standards, and TC's related to PROBONO is supposed to raise awareness within the PROBONO consortium of the opportunities that standardization can provide for R&I projects. This is the essential basis to develop a standardization strategy (ST9.4.2) for PROBONO and to later implement corresponding standardization activities (ST9.4.3).

1 Introduction

1.1 Mapping PROBONO outputs

The purpose of this section is to map PROBONO's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs, and work performed (Table 1).

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 9.4. Standardization activities (M1-M60)	ST9.4.1 Investigate relevant standards. Conduct research on and basic assessment of published standards, standards under development, relevant technical committees, and further standardization activities at European and international level, e.g., CEN, CENELEC, ISO, and IEC covering the needs of sustainable green neighbourhoods, followed by an evaluation by the consortium members	1.3.3 WT3 Work package description	Within this deliverable a general overview of the standardization landscape for PROBONO is given. Besides a focus on already existing standards, relevant standardization committees for PROBONO are highlighted both on international and European level.
DELIVERABLE			
D9.7: PROBONO Standardization (I) This report formulates the findings of T9.4, and explores step/s A) Report on current standardization landscape			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.

1.2 Purpose and scope of the document

The PROBONO project is about implementing Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBN) in European districts. To establish a GBN framework in a general sense and to develop state-of-the-art solutions for PROBONO, compliance with standards is beneficial. Adherence to standards within the project also ensures trustworthiness. For this reason, PROBONO has integrated standardization as an essential element in the project. Standardization is integrated in the project as a separate Task 9.4 – *Standardization activities* within WP9 – *Replicability, Exploitation & Commercialisation*. This deliverable, which is the first of three within Task 9.4, provides a general overview of the standardization landscape for PROBONO. In general, this standardization overview serves as the basis for further standardization activities in PROBONO. Knowing about existing standardization documents makes it possible to build up on existing knowledge and avoid unnecessary duplication of work. In addition, existing gaps in

standardization can be better identified and impulses for new standardization activities can be developed.

1.3 Structure of the document and its relation with other WPS/Deliverables

In contrast to patents, knowledge about standardization is less pronounced, especially in research and innovation. For this reason, the basic principles of standardization are presented in this report (see clause 2) as well as the different facets of standardization at international (subclause 2.2), European (subclause 2.3) and national level (subclause 2.4). Subsequently, the various types of standardization documents (subclause 2.1), the function of standardization in the context of research projects (subclause 2.5), and the process for creating a CWA (subclause 2.1) are presented in more detail. The results of the standardization research for PROBONO are presented by explaining the approach for standards research (clause 3) and finally giving an overview of the related standardization landscape (clause 4). Besides a general overview of the standardization landscape of PROBONO (clause 4.1), the relevant international (subclause 4.2) and European (subclause 4.3) standardization activities are examined. The standards which could be relevant for the project are focused on more closely (subclause 4.4) with regard to the most interesting areas for PROBONO.

In general, this deliverable shall provide a basis for the work in all WP's of PROBONO. Nevertheless, at this point it could be especially useful for WP1 to contribute in the definition of the GBN framework and of the applied methodologies. A short introduction was given in the D1.1 already, which is also included in this deliverable in a more extended and also updated version. Since this deliverable covers standardization in various areas related to PROBONO, it can be helpful for all WP to define concepts, use methods which are already established, and rely on technology solutions which are widely accepted by experts in the different areas.

1.4 Contribution to creating GBN

This deliverable contributes to the creation of the GBN framework by providing an overview of the existing standards in this context. Those standards can be used as a basis to develop PROBONO concepts and solutions. The work items for the topic of “sustainable cities and communities”, which are currently under development at international level, are also listed in this deliverable and should be considered for the work within PROBONO.

Besides using standards for the development of PROBONO solutions, at a later stage of the project it is also intended to integrate PROBONO results into new or ongoing standardization activities. This would be beneficial for future projects in that area. To ensure that these results are relevant for standardization, an exchange with PROBONO's sister projects may be useful to find common ground especially with regard to GBN.

2 Standardization

2.1 General

Within the PROBONO project the standardization part can support technology development as well as ethical implications and social aspects. Therefore, it is important to clarify what a standard actually is. In general, a standard is a consensus-based document that is approved by a recognized body. It provides rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, reflecting the state-of-the art. It should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology and experience, and aim to promote optimal community benefits.¹⁰ Standardization as an important strategic tool is used to agree on terminologies, methodologies, requirements, characteristics, etc. in specific areas to make a product, process, or service fit for its purpose. Thus, standardization can drive innovative outcomes by agreeing on common product requirements such as interoperability, quality or safety, and provide guidelines for achieving them. Standardization can support the creation of a generic language, which is understandable for everyone and thus helps to create a common understanding. The result of the standardization process is a document, which provides rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results. The benefits of these documents and their applications vary and depend on the different types of documents (Figure 1). The differences between these types of documents lie in their development procedure together with the degree of consensus which has to be reached, and the openness to participation.

¹⁰ CEN/CENELEC, „EN 45020:2006: Standardization and related activities - General vocabulary,“ 2006

Figure 1: Types of standardization documents.

According to Figure 1, **standards** in the narrower sense are developed within the formal standardization system where all interested parties have to be included in the development process of the document and consensus, meaning the general agreement of all participants and the lack of sustained objection to central content, must be reached. The main objective of the consensus is to take into account the views of all interested parties concerned and to dispel any counter-arguments. The development of a European standard is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Development of a standard.

First of all, anyone who has identified a need for a standard can submit a standardization proposal. The associated standards committee evaluates the need and checks whether standardization activities are already taking place or if standards covering the described need already exist. If a need is identified, a standard is then developed in a standards committee. Attention is paid to a balanced composition of these committees with all interested parties concerned (science, consumers, industry, ...) in order to guarantee the neutrality of the documents. When a finished draft has been approved by the standards committee, it is released

for commenting by the public. The comments are finally discussed and then the final standard is published by consensus. Due to the high level of transparency and the involvement of the public, the development time increases from national to European / international level. National standards usually require 18 months to develop. The development of European and international standards takes more than two years due to the national standards bodies having to form an opinion in their respective mirror committees and vote on whether they support the European or international standard.¹¹ Due to the high degree of consensus, standards have a high level of acceptance in society. There are various types of existing standards, focusing on different topics of interest, e.g. terminology or testing.

In contrast to a standard created with consensus, the standardization activities in research projects focus on the creation of **specifications**. A specification is a publicly available document that describes products, systems or services by defining characteristics and requirements. It is characterized by the fact that, compared to a standard, a consensus is not absolutely necessary and the involvement of all interested parties is not obligatory. The creation of a specification, e.g. CWA, a so-called pre-standard, is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Development of a specification.

Again, anyone can submit an application to develop a specification. A standardization organization checks internally whether standards conflicting with the application exist. If no conflicting standards exist, the standardization organization publishes the business plan for

¹¹ <https://www.iso.org/developing-standards.html>

public comment and a call for cooperation from interested organizations. In contrast to standards, specifications are created in workshops (temporary committee) with a standardization organization acting as a secretary. This committee also decides whether a draft should be published for comment and once a specification has successfully been adopted by the committee, it is published by a standardization organization. There are different types of specifications. A Workshop Agreement on European (CWA) or international (IWA) level is developed in a temporary workshop which is designed to meet an immediate need and forms the basis for future standardization activities lead by a national standardization body. Even if there are not as strict rules for developing a specification as there are for standards, it is important to ensure the coherence of the standardization regulations to protect the credibility of international, European, and national standardization. The workshop is open for direct participation to anyone with an interest in the development of the agreement but no full consensus is needed. The development of a Workshop Agreement is fast and flexible, on average between 10 and 12 months and therefore also attractive for research projects. The different national standardization organizations each have their own name for these specifications that have been developed in workshops, e.g., a nationally created pre-standard by DIN (Germany) is called DIN SPEC (e.g., DIN SPEC 91392). Specifications can also be developed within standards committees if, for example, no final consensus can be reached. These documents are then referred to as CEN or ISO TS (Technical Specifications). A TS on European level may not conflict with a European standard but conflicting national standards may continue to exist. Technical Reports (TR) are informal documents that are developed and approved by a technical committee. A TR provides information on technical content and standardization work.

Regarding the development time, the fastest ones are the **de-facto-standards** (see *Figure 1*), also called industry or consortia standards. Among other things, they are characterized by the fact that not all interested parties need to be included in the creation process. These closed group of experts can be, e. g. industry-specific consortia that have been formed from different companies. Although these documents have some characteristics of a standardization document such as defined procedures or documentation rules, de-facto-standards are often not freely accessible and are developed in private.

Every country participating in the European and international standardization world of CEN, CENELEC, ISO, and IEC follows the so called delegation principle. National standardization bodies, such as DIN in Germany, UNE in the Spain or BSI in the UK send representatives to the

European or international standardization committees of CEN, CENELEC, ISO, and IEC to represent their national interests (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Overview of the organizational structure of the standardization world.

An essential aspect of standardization work is to ensure that documents do not contradict each other, especially since European and international standardization has gained significantly in importance, as reflected in DIN's statistics, which show that European and international standards account for 90% of all standardization projects nowadays. The following clauses give a brief description of the framework of formal standardization on international, European, and national level. Furthermore, the relevance of standardization in R&I project is considered.

2.2 International standardization level

The international standardization organizations ISO¹² (International Organization for Standardization), IEC¹³ (International Electrotechnical Commission), and ITU¹⁴ (International Telecommunication Union) are responsible for organizing international standardization work. ISO is responsible for all non-electronic and IEC for electrotechnical standardization activities while the ITU is in charge of standardization activities in the field of telecommunications on an international level.

¹² www.iso.org

¹³ <https://www.iec.ch/>

¹⁴ <https://www.itu.int>

ISO and IEC are made up of the national standardization organizations, with e.g. DIN and DKE representing German interests on an international level. The ITU, on the other hand, is a special unit of the United Nations, whose 191 member states develop recommendations together with companies from the private sector and other regional and national organizations. Only when they are adopted by normative organizations such as ISO, ANSI (USA) or ETSI as well as by national regulatory authorities such as the Federal Network Agency in Germany do they acquire the character of standards.

The so-called delegation principle applies to ISO and IEC, meaning that the national standardization organizations send their experts to the international standardization bodies. Here, the work is discussed in a national mirror committee, existing results are discussed, a national opinion is developed and the final draft standards are agreed upon. Only when a sufficiently large majority of the national standardization organizations has voted for a draft standard is it accepted and published as an international standard (ISO). International specifications are referred to as IWA as well as ISO TS or IEC TS, depending on the type of creation.

In contrast to European standardization, there is no obligation to adopt international standards in national standards. However, since internationally applicable standards are relevant for international trade or for global stakeholders, conflicting national or European standards should be avoided. There is the possibility of incorporating international standards in European and national standards and there are also parallel creation processes of standards at international and European level. The resulting documents have the characteristics and names listed in Table 2, depending on the background.

Name	Description
ISO XXXXX	International standard neither nationally nor European adopted
DIN ISO XXXXX	International standard only nationally (Germany) adopted
DIN EN ISO XXXXX	International standard adopted on European and national level

Table 2: Names of international standards depending on their adoption level.

2.3 European standardization level

The main goal of standardization at European level is to harmonize the national standards of the member states of the European Union (EU). This includes on the one hand the uniform transfer of international standards and on the other hand the creation of European standards. The European standardization organizations CEN¹⁵ (European Committee for Standardization), CENELEC¹⁶ (European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization) and ETSI¹⁷ (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) are responsible for the organization of European standardization work. CEN is responsible for all non-electronic activities and CENELEC for electrotechnical standardization activities, while ETSI is responsible for the standardization activities in the field of telecommunications at European level.

There is a particularly close cooperation between CEN and CENELEC, which are made up of national standardization organizations from the EU and EFTA (European Free Trade Association) member states, e.g. Germany's interests being represented by DIN and DKE, as well as the states seeking membership. In contrast, the members of ETSI are directly European companies, institutes and organizations.

The so-called delegation principle applies to CEN and CENELEC, meaning that the members, the national standardization bodies, send their national experts to a European standardization body at CEN or CENELEC. In a national committee, known as the mirror committee, the work and existing results are discussed and a national opinion is developed. This committee then votes on the final draft standards. Only when a sufficiently large majority of the national standardization organizations has voted for a draft standard is it accepted and published as a European standard (EN standard).

European standards must automatically be adopted by the member states of the EU and opposing national standards withdrawn. As a result of this adoption obligation, the EN standards in Germany then become DIN EN standards (e.g. DIN EN 16575). European specifications are referred to as CWA as well as CEN TS or CENELEC TS, depending on the type of creation. The obligation to adopt the national standards of the member countries does not apply to specifications, but is possible (e.g. DIN CEN/TS 17045).

¹⁵ www.cen.eu

¹⁶ www.cenelec.eu

¹⁷ www.etsi.org

For PROBONO in particular, aspects of standardization play an important role. The European research framework program Horizon 2020 addresses the topic of standardization in a series of calls for proposals.

2.4 National standardization level

On the national level, there are different structures and standardization bodies in different countries, as e. g. British Standards Institute (BSI), German Institute for Standardization (DIN), Spanish standardization body (UNE). In general, each country has a recognized national standardization body (NSB) which represents the national opinion at international / European level. Each national standardization body can develop national standards as long as there is no EN standard existing on a particular area. There are situations in which it is possible to complement EN standards with additional national standards, for instance to set more detailed requirements suiting to specific needs of the member state.

An important country outside of Europe, which must be taken into account in the context of standardization are the USA. The United States (US) standardization landscape differs somehow from the European approach. The American National Standards Institute (ANSI) is a private, non-profit organization that oversees the development of voluntary consensus standards for products, services, processes, systems, and personnel in the US. The organization also coordinates US standards with international standards. ANSI accredits standards that are developed by representatives of other standards organizations, government agencies, consumer groups, companies, and others.¹⁸ It works as kind of umbrella organization by coordinating 240 Standards Developing Organizations (SDOs), such as Underwriter Laboratories (UL), American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME), Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE). Many of them develop standards for the US-market and provide certification or accreditation services as well, e. g. UL. The American Society for Testing and Material (ASTM), which is an ANSI-accredited standards developer,¹⁹ is another important national standardization body in the US. Some standards are implemented in the federal laws, others are

¹⁸ <https://ansi.org/american-national-standards/ans-introduction/overview>

¹⁹

<https://share.ansi.org/Shared%20Documents/Standards%20Activities/American%20National%20Standards/ANSI%20Accredited%20Standards%20Developers/DEC2022ASD.pdf>

viewed more as guidelines for industry. This is the case for many of the standards developed by US-SDOs.

The PROBONO consortium includes the participation of one national standardization body – DIN.

2.5 Standardization in research projects

It is crucial for an R&I project to know the state of the art in the areas relevant for or connected to the project. Since standards reflect this state of the art in a specific area it is essential for R&I projects to have an overview of the standardization landscape related to the project. This knowledge enables the project to adapt its results such as products, services, etc. to the current needs. R&I projects need to consider what is being developed within other relevant activities. Irrespective of the technical merits of the R&I project developments, these efforts will be inconsequential if developed in isolation and the market decides to follow another path. Furthermore, the knowledge about related standards also enables the R&I project to overcome additional challenges and go beyond the current state of the art. On the one hand, an overview of the related standardization landscape offers an R&I project the advantages described above. On the other hand, awareness is raised on where standardization is still needed. This opportunity can be used by the R&I project to implement project results in already ongoing standardization activities or by developing new standards out of project results.

3 Methodology: How the PROBONO standardization landscape was developed

3.1 General

This clause describes how the standardization landscape relevant for the PROBONO project was developed. A standardization landscape for a specific topic provides an overview of the existing standards relevant and related to the defined topic(s). Such an overview of the standardization landscape for PROBONO should raise awareness among the project partners on what is already on the market and avoids them to re-invent the wheel. Further, the standardization landscape provides the basis for working with standards for the duration of the project. The approach to develop a standardization landscape is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Steps for the development of a standardization landscape.

The basis for providing a standardization landscape for the consortium is the standards research where all the relevant standards for the project are collected. To perform such standards research, in a first step, areas were defined in relation with the topics of PROBONO that are also relevant for the project partners. In a next step the project partners were asked to provide keywords for those areas. Those keywords were used to search existing standards (standards research) by using the standards data base Nautos²⁰. The list of found standards which present the standardization landscape for PROBONO was then spread in the form of a dashboard (see subclause 4.1). The details of this procedure within PROBONO are described in the following paragraphs.

²⁰ <https://nautos.de/>

Besides the need to define within PROBONO the Green Building Neighbourhood (GBN) Framework (WP1) the different WP's and Tasks relate to the GBN-topic in various approaches. Thus, the first step was to analyse where the project partners need an overview of the existing standards in a specific area within PROBONO. To examine this, the procedure was twofold. First, a survey was spread within the consortium where 24 answers were received. To allow everyone from the consortium to include their view, as a second step a standardization session within the first GA was organized. Both, the survey and the standardization session were also used to evaluate who from the partners is already active in the field of standardization and which standards are also already in use within the consortium. In this way the partners level of knowledge on standardisation was assessed to properly design future actions in this task.

3.2 Survey on standardization

The survey on standardization was shared in October 2022 (see Annex A.1). This survey was answered by 24 partners from 20 organisations and served to get a first impression on the relation of the partners to the topic of standardization. Since the partners who answered the survey are active in all WP's a rough but broad overview was received for the PROBONO consortium. The vast majority of those partners (92 %) is already applying or plans to apply standards within their activities in PROBONO. The areas where those standards are / will be applied are given in Table 5 together with the results from the standardization workshop. More than half of the participants (54 %) indicated that they would need an overview of the available standards for a specific area within PROBONO. The stated areas in which such an overview on standards is needed are summarized in Table 3.

Topic area	Area
Buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration batteries in buildings • Local Building Codes & Products or system requirements • Indoor environmental quality
Digital solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital twin architecture • IOT architecture • Data management • Building Information Management (BIM)
Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycled raw materials
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life-cycle assessment (LCA)
Mobility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electric vehicle charging • Electric mobility

Topic area	Area
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility data collection
Others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of the planned innovations (mechanical, electrical local codes) • Construction Permits in Ireland, Portugal and Spain • COVID-19

Table 3: Areas in which an overview of standards is needed for the work within PROBONO.

Those questions laid the basis for performing the standards research leading to the overview of the standardization landscape for PROBONO. Since this is only the first step within the standardization task in PROBONO which is aiming at contributing to standardization activities on European or international level, the survey queried also if the project partners already see the need to standardize something due to missing standards in an area. This was affirmed by 21 % of the partners. The suggested topics are listed in Table 6 together with the results from the standardization session in the following subclause.

To assess the knowledge about standardization within the consortium the partners where asked if they have been / are active in a standardization committee and if yes in which one. Nearly one third of the partners (29 %) who answered the survey are active in a Technical Committee (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Since within R&I project the development of specifications is usually a first step into standardization the participants of the survey were also asked if somebody already was involved in the development of a pre-standard like a CWA. 8 % of the partners answered this question with yes.

The last question of the survey queried what expectations the project partners for the PROBONO standardization activities have. Around 17 % of the partners have expectations and indicated them. Besides the information of the project partners regarding standardization activities and learning what standardization means to PROBONO the need for support in the application of standards and the identification of standardization gaps was mentioned. Further, it is expected that within the standardization task operational and reproducible standards are identified to help take action. Therefore, standardization is supposed to help PROBONO to be more consistent and unlock scale. The answers are completely in accordance with what is planned within the Task 9.4 – Standardization Activities in PROBONO.

3.3 Standardization session within the GA

To share basic knowledge about standardization and inform the consortium about the planned activities within the standardization task, a standardization session was conducted at the general assembly (GA) on 22nd February 2023 in Chania, Greece. The slides of that presentation can be found in Annex A.2. Besides informing about the main facts on standardization and giving a first impression of the standardization landscape for GBN this standardization session was used to conduct a standardization workshop. The aim of this workshop was to complement the answers from the survey which lays the basis for the standards research and therefore the standardization landscape for PROBONO. During the GA around 70 PROBONO partners were present. Within the standardization session those who did not had the chance to fill in the survey also had the opportunity to provide input for the standards research and this way to the standardization landscape for PROBONO.

To complete the overview of who from the consortium is already active in the field of standardization, the present partners were asked if they have ever been or are currently active in a standardization committee. Additional 5 answers were received and listed in **Error! Reference source not found.** together with the responses from the survey. The table shows that some of the PROBONO partners are / were already actively involved in the standardization process in one or another way and therefore have some knowledge about standardization.

Level	Technical Committee
National	Spain: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several UNE committees related with gas pipes and HVAC systems • CTN 203/SC 21/GT 1 Second life of mobility batteries for stationary uses Denmark: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dansk Standard S-454 Standardization committee for electric vehicles France: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AFNOR Smart City Technical committee Ireland: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NSAI
European	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEN/TC226 WG12 Road equipment - Road interaction - ADAS / Autonomous vehicles • Expert guest for EN 14500, EN 14501 • CEN/TC 254 Flexible sheets for waterproofing • CEN/CLC/JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence • Involved in CWA development

Level	Technical Committee
International	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expert guest for ISO 19467 • ISO/TC 254 Safety of amusement rides and amusement devices • ISO/TC 21 Equipment for fire protection and fire fighting • Contribution to ITU-T Y.4205 Requirements and reference model of IoT-related crowdsourced systems • ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment

Table 4: Standardization Committees were PROBONO partners are / have been active.

To complement the information from the survey for the standards research during the standardization session the participants were working in six groups on flipcharts with one person per group who took over the writing task. In a first step, the areas from the survey (see Table 3) were presented and the consortium was asked to name further relevant topic areas where an overview of the standardization landscape is necessary. Those new collected areas together with those from the survey were written separately on one page of the flipchart. An overview of the topic areas and subordinated areas is mapped in Figure 6. In a second step each group was asked to collect relevant keywords for each area. An overview of the summarized results from all groups can be found in Annex A.4

Figure 6: Topic areas and subordinated areas for the keyword collection.

With the help of the keywords a standards research was conducted for the different topic areas. Those standards presenting the standardization landscape for PROBONO were summarized in a dashboard and shared with the project partners. The standardization landscape is described in detail in the following clause 4 of this deliverable.

During the standardization session it was also planned to ask the partners which standards they are already using within PROBONO and if they already see a need for standardization. Due to

time issues within the workshop this part was skipped and instead included in another survey which was send to the consortium after the standardization session (see Annex A.3). The survey was answered by 22 partners. Table 5 lists the standards which are already used within PROBONO from both surveys. Obviously, already many standards are used within the different areas related to PROBONO. Especially in the area of buildings many national standards are used. National standards are not in the focus of this deliverable with regard to the standardization landscape but will be included eventually according to the needs of the consortium, especially from the LL. Within the topic area of digital solutions also de-facto standards were mentioned where a lot of activities are ongoing.

Topic area	Area
Battery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 62208:2011 Empty enclosures for low-voltage switchgear and controlgear assemblies - General requirements (IEC 62208:2011) • IEC 62619:2022 Secondary cells and batteries containing alkaline or other non-acid electrolytes - Safety requirements for secondary lithium cells and batteries, for use in industrial applications • UN Transport Test UN38.3 • Regulation 2017/2102/EU • Regulation 2014/30/EU • Regulation 2014/35/EU • IEC 61439-1:2020 Low-voltage switchgear and controlgear assemblies - Part 1: General rules • IEC 61000-6-2:2016 Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) - Part 6-2: Generic standards - Immunity standard for industrial environments • IEC 61000-6-4:2013 Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) - Part 4-6: Testing and measurement techniques - Immunity to conducted disturbances, induced by radio-frequency fields • IEC 61439 series: Low-voltage switchgear and controlgear assemblies • IEC 61000 series: Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) • IEC 62619:2022 Secondary cells and batteries containing alkaline or other non- acid electrolytes - Safety requirements for secondary lithium cells and batteries, for use in industrial applications
Biodiversity	
Buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buildings codes • Fire resistance

Topic area	Area
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thermal insulation • Waterproofing (membrane) • Thermal conductivity • Indoor environmental quality • EN 15026:2007 - Hygrothermal performance of building components and building elements — Assessment of moisture transfer by numerical simulation • ISO 19650 series: Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) - Information management using building information modelling • ISO 16739 series: Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) for data sharing in the construction and facility management industries • Country specific building standards for roofs • ISO 20887:2020 Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works - Design for disassembly and adaptability - Principles, requirements and guidance • EN 1401:2019 Plastics piping systems for non-pressure underground drainage and sewerage - Unplasticized poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC-U) - Part 1: Specifications for pipes, fittings and the systems • ISO/IEC 11801 series: Information technology - Generic cabling for customer premises • Spanish Technical Building Code (CTE) • Spanish Regulation on Low and High Voltage and its Technical Notes (ITC - RAT and LAT standards) • UNE Electrical Standards • IBERDROLA Specifications (electricity supply company) • Spanish Standard for Thermal Installations • Canal de Isabel II Regulations for sewage systems • Municipal Bylaws • Spanish Regulation on Fire Fighting • UNE 23007 series: Fire detection and fire alarm systems
Digital solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical standards such as protocols (wifi, http) and data types (JSON.LD, rdf) • FMU (Functional MockUp Unit) to export Reduced Order Models

Topic area	Area
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) • WMS (Web Map Service) • WCS (Web Coverage Service) • DevOps standards • UML (Unified Modeling Language) use case • Smart Applications REference (SAREF) ontology • IEEE 802.3at Power over Ethernet enhancements (25.5 W) • IEEE 802.1b: Management of local area network and metropolitan area network • IEEE 802.1q: Virtual Local Area Network (VPN) • IEEE 802.11: Telecommunications and information exchange between systems- Local and metropolitan area networks- Specific requirements: Part 11: Media access control for wireless networks and physical layer specifications • EN 300267 series: Integrated Services Digital Network (ISDN) - Telephony 7 kHz, videotelephony, audiographic conference and videoconference teleservices; Digital Subscriber Signalling System No. one (DSS1) protocol • ISO/IEC 18092:2013 Information technology - Telecommunications and information exchange between systems - Near Field Communication - Interface and Protocol (NFCIP-1) • UML (Unified Modelling Language) • Digital Twins • Information Management
Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 50001:2018 Energy management systems - Requirements with guidance for use • UNE 100715-1:2014 Guide for the design, implementation and monitoring of a geothermal system. Part 1: Vertical closed circuit systems • EN 13941-1:2021 District heating pipes - Design and installation of thermal insulated bonded single and twin pipe systems for directly buried hot water networks - Part 1: Design • Renewable energy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ UNE 100715-1:2014 Guide for the design, implementation and monitoring of a geothermal system. Part 1: Vertical closed circuit system ○ EN 50583 series: Photovoltaics in buildings

Topic area	Area
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy consumption
Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DS/EN 206 DK NA:2020 Concrete – Specification, performance, production and conformity – Rules for application of EN 206 in Denmark • Building materials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EN 12620:2002+A1:2008 (Aggregates for concrete) ○ EN 206:2013+A2:2021 (Concrete - Specification, performance, production and conformity) • Raw materials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mobility recycled raw materials
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life-cycle assessment (LCA) • Life-cycle cost (LCC) • Social life-cycle assessment (s-LCA) • International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP) • Stakeholder analysis
Mobility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electric vehicle charging • Mobility data collection
Others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 37100:2016 Sustainable cities and communities – Vocabulary • ISO 14122-3:2016 Safety of machinery - Permanent means of access to machinery - Part 3: Stairs, stepladders and guard-rails • ISO 14122-4:2016 Safety of machinery - Permanent means of access to machinery - Part 4: Fixed ladders • NTP 1160:2021 Fixed Scales of Service • ANSI/TIA/EIA-568-B: Telecommunications standard in commercial buildings • EN 50132-7:2012 Alarm systems - CCTV surveillance systems for use in security applications - Part 7: Application guidelines • IEC 14443 series: Cards and security devices for personal identification - Contactless proximity objects • EN 50130 series: Alarm systems • EN 50131 series: Alarm systems - Intrusion and hold-up systems • CO₂-emissions • Green procurement • COVID-19

Table 5: Standards which are / will be applied within PROBONO.

In Table 6 the areas are listed where there already could be identified a need for standardization since there the PROBONO partners are missing standards. The topic of standardization needs will be covered within a separate workshop in the standardization task of PROBONO where the potential to standardize PROBONO results will be analysed. For this Table 6 can be used as a basis.

Topic area	Area
Digital solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • digital twins and green neighbourhoods • Dual Distributed Network • common geometric processing tool for BIM • data exchange between energy communities • ontologies for data interoperability by design
Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can we reuse materials and comply with the law/regulations? • re-use material as new building element • standard for environmental product declaration (EPDs) for re-used materials • categorizing the reuse potential of existing building parts • standard which can categorize a building's ability to be disassembly (design for disassembly) • fungi & bacterial resistance of biobased materials in accordance with their uses
Mobility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • mobility data collection
Others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • epidemics mitigation - standardization around the contagious diseases mitigation blueprints • information Exchange between project partners • a standard ontology for GBN • impact evaluation

Table 6: Areas where standards are missing within PROBONO.

4 Overview of the PROBONO standardization landscape

4.1 General

This clause gives an overview of the standardization landscape related to the PROBONO project. Besides providing a general overview on the standards which could be relevant for PROBONO details on which standardization committees are active in the fields interesting for PROBONO are given. With the use of the provided keywords altogether 482 standards were found including those mentioned from the survey which are already used by the consortium. These standards represent the first overview of the standardization landscape for PROBONO and were therefore shared with the partners in form of a dashboard (Figure 7). The dashboard is an Excel template, which was developed specifically for the research of standards and provides an overview of the main information regarding the relevant standards. It can be used to search for specific standards by keywords or to get an overview of the standards within a specific ICS field or developed by a specific TC. This dashboard was shared within the whole PROBONO consortium. Since the development of standards does not stand still, the dashboard will be updated annually.

Figure 7: PROBONO standards dashboard.

The dashboard is also used to provide some general information on the standards possibly relevant to the PROBONO project. In Figure 8 the origin of the documents included in the PROBONO dashboard is visualized. The majority (71%) of the standards was developed on international level, whereas around 29% originated on European level and the minority of below 1% on national level. The reason for the small number of national standards added to the

standardization dashboard is that national standards were mostly excluded during the standards research. PROBONO is a European research project and therefore individual national standards are for the first overview of the standardization landscape of secondary importance. National standards will be added to this overview in accordance with the needs of the project partners. Therefore, in the following subclauses only standards on international and European level are looked at. In Figure 9 the type of the listed standardization documents is broken down. 76% of the documents included in the dashboard are standards in the narrower sense (see subclause 2.1) like ISO- / EN- or national standards whereas the rest are specifications. Nearly 65% of the documents were published / revised within the last 5 years.

Figure 8: Level of standards.

Figure 9: Type of standardization documents.

The standards related to the PROBONO project cover a wide range of different areas. Based on the ICS (International Classification for Standards) fields, an overview of the different areas can be given (Figure 7). For this overview only ICS fields which are assigned to at least 10 standards are listed in Figure 7. The standards are part of 8 different ICS fields, whereas 13 – *Environment. Health protection. Safety*, 35 – *Information technology*, 03 – *Services. Company organization. Management and quality. Administration. Transport. Sociology* and 43 – *Road vehicles engineering* are the most present ones. It is important to keep in mind, that one standard can be part of a number of different ICS fields. 20% of the standards included in the PROBONO dashboard are classified within the ICS field 13.020 – *Environmental protection*. Nearly the same amount (19%) of standards is included in 35.240 – *Application of information technology*. The third biggest number of standards (10%) are part of 43.120 – *Electric road vehicles* and 03.100 – *Company organization and management. Management systems*.

ICS-field		Number of standards
01 – Generalities. Terminology. Standardization. Documentation	01.040 - Vocabularies	18
03 – Services. Company organization. Management and quality. Administration. Transport. Sociology	03.100 – Company organization and management. Management systems	48
	03.220 - Transport	21
13 – Environment. Health protection. Safety	13.020 – Environmental protection	98
	13.320 – Alarm and warning systems	12
	13.030 - Wastes	10
	13.180 - Ergonomics	10
27 – Energy and heat transfer engineering	27.015 – Energy efficiency. Energy conservation in general	18
33 – Telecommunications. Audio and video engineering	33.040 – Telecommunication systems	18
	33.200 – Telecontrol. Telemetry	15
35 – Information technology	35.240 – Application of information technology	93
	35.200 – Interface and interconnection equipment	28
	35.020 – Information technology (IT) in general	22
	35.030 – IT security	16
43 – Road vehicles engineering	43.120 – Electric road vehicles	49
	43.040 – Road vehicle systems	13
91 – Construction materials and building	91.010 – Construction industry	19
	91.040 - Buildings	15

Table 7: Overview of the number of standards in the different ICS fields.

4.2 Standardization activities on international level

From the standards which could be relevant for the PROBONO project 341 documents from international level were included in the PROBONO dashboard. The main technical committees, which are responsible for these standards are listed in Table 8 and are described in the following.

Only those TC's which published 10 or more standards which are included in the dashboard are listed and described below.

ISO/IEC JTC 1	Information technology
ISO/TC 268	Sustainable cities and communities
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
ISO/TC 292	Security and resilience
ISO/TC 22	Road vehicles
ISO/TC 59	Buildings and civil engineering works
IEC/TC 69	Electrical power/energy transfer systems for electrically propelled road vehicles and industrial trucks

Table 8: Relevant standard setting organizations and TC's on international level.

The **ISO/IEC JTC1 – Information Technology**²¹ founded in 1987 is a joint technical committee from ISO and IEC focusing on the development of ICT standards for business and consumer applications.²² It has already published 3395 ISO/IEC standards, whereas nearly 500 are currently under development.²¹ Regarding the related international standards for PROBONO, 79 of them were developed by this JTC. Under the direct responsibility of this JTC 29 standards were developed whereas the others were developed within subcommittees. ISO/IEC JTC1 is composed of 23 sub committees whereas the most relevant ones are described in the following:

SC 42 – *Artificial intelligence developed* 11 of those standards. This SC was created in 2017 and serves as the focus and proponent for JTC 1's standardization program on Artificial Intelligence. It provides guidance to JTC 1, IEC, and ISO committees developing Artificial Intelligence applications. This SC already published 17 ISO standards whereas 27 are under development.²³

SC27 - *Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection* published 8 of the related standards. This SC was created in 1989 and aims to develop standards for the protection of information and ICT. This includes generic methods, techniques and guidelines to address both

²¹ <https://www.iso.org/committee/45020.html>

²² <https://jtc1info.org/sd-2-history/>

²³ <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

security and privacy aspects. There are already 229 standards which were published by this SC and 67 are under development.²⁴

SC25 - *Interconnection of information technology equipment* published 7 of the standards. It was created in 1990. Its scope includes standardization of microprocessor systems, interfaces, protocols, architectures and associated interconnecting media for information technology equipment and networks to support embedded and distributed computing environments, storage systems and other input/output components. Further, standards for home and building electronic systems in residential and commercial environments to support interworking devices (IoT-related) and applications such as energy management, environmental control, lighting, and security are developed. In addition, cabling system standards for information and communication technology (ICT), in all types of residential, commercial and industrial environments for the design, planning and installation, test procedures, automated infrastructure management systems and remote powering are provided. This SC published 224 standards whereas one is under development.²⁵

SC41 - *Internet of things and digital twin* published 7 of the standards with relation to PROBONO. After the creation in 2017 its scope is standardization in the area of Internet of Things and related technologies. It serves as the focus and proponent for JTC 1's standardization programme on the Internet of Things and Digital Twin, including their related technologies. Therefore, it provides guidance to JTC 1, IEC, ISO and other entities developing Internet of Things and Digital Twin related applications.²⁶

From **ISO/TC 268 - Sustainable cities and communities** 39 of the standards in the dashboard were published. On international level, this seems to be the most relevant TC in a general sense for the PROBONO project. Its secretariat is hold by AFNOR (France). With the development of this committee in 2012, the standardization in the field of sustainable cities and communities started. The scope of this TC is standardization in the field of sustainable cities and communities including the development of requirements, frameworks, guidance and supporting techniques and tools related to the achievement of sustainable development considering smartness and resilience. This is intended to help cities and communities as well as other interested parties in

²⁴ <https://www.iso.org/committee/45306.html>

²⁵ <https://www.iso.org/committee/45270.html>

²⁶ <https://www.iso.org/committee/6483279.html>

rural and urban areas to become more sustainable.²⁷ In doing so, ISO/TC 268 contributes to the UN Sustainable Development Goals especially goal 11 which aims to make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.²⁸ ISO/TC 268 has 34 participating members and 36 observing members. The structure of this TC is displayed in Figure 10. It consists of two sub committees and seven working groups.²⁷

Figure 10: Overview of the structure of ISO/TC 268.

The standardization work of subcommittee *ISO/TC 268/SC 1 - Smart community infrastructures* whose secretariat is held by Japan includes basic concepts to define and describe smartness of community infrastructure as an integrative large-scale product, harmonized metrics for benchmarking, usage of the metrics for application to the diverse types of communities, and specifications for measurement/reporting/verification. Hereby, the focus is on the technical aspects of smart community infrastructure, which are basic structures that support the operation and activities of urban communities, e.g. energy, water, resource management systems, ICT infrastructure. The concept of smartness is addressed in terms of performance relevant to technologically implementable solutions, based on multiple aspects including sustainability.²⁹

The second subcommittee *ISO/TC 268/SC 2 - Sustainable mobility and transportation* whose secretariat is also held by Japan and aims to promote as well as support a multi-sectorial integrated approach of sustainable cities and communities with a long-term vision. Further, organizational issues, infrastructures and services in the mobility and transportation options for

²⁷ <https://www.iso.org/committee/656906.html>

²⁸ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal11>

²⁹ <https://www.iso.org/committee/656967.html>

cities and communities, including those related to new technologies (i.e. electric, hydrogen, autonomous) are considered. The standards developed in this subcommittee shall provide requirements, frameworks, guidance and supporting techniques and tools for cities and territories, as well as all mobility and transportation stakeholders to plan, develop, operate, maintain and manage sustainable mobility and transportation systems and services with a long-term vision.

The ISO/TC 268 in general already published 42 standards and 16 standards are now under development.²⁷ These standards are listed in Table 9 and Table 10. For the PROBONO project these standards are important since they form the overall and general basis for all the work which will be done during the project lifetime. It is also important to know which standards are coming in the next few months to implement them in the development processes and be in accordance with them. For doing so, the 13 standards developed under the direct responsibility of ISO/TC 268 were provided for the consortium as a basis to work with.

Document No.	Title	TC
ISO 37100:2016	Sustainable cities and communities — Vocabulary	ISO/TC 268
ISO 37101:2016	Sustainable development in communities — Management system for sustainable development — Requirements with guidance for use	
ISO 37104:2019	Sustainable cities and communities — Transforming our cities — Guidance for practical local implementation of ISO 37101	
ISO 37105:2019	Sustainable cities and communities — Descriptive framework for cities and communities	
ISO 37106:2021	Sustainable cities and communities — Guidance on establishing smart city operating models for sustainable communities	
ISO/TS 37107:2019	Sustainable cities and communities — Maturity model for smart sustainable communities	
ISO 37108:2022	Sustainable cities and communities — Business districts — Guidance for practical local implementation of ISO 37101	
ISO 37109:2023	Sustainable cities and communities — Recommendations and requirements for project developers — Meeting ISO 37101 framework principles	

Document No.	Title	TC
ISO 37110:2022	Sustainable cities and communities — Management requirements and recommendations for open data for smart cities and communities — Overview and general principles	
ISO 37120:2018	Sustainable cities and communities — Indicators for city services and quality of life	
ISO/TR 37121:2017	Sustainable development in communities — Inventory of existing guidelines and approaches on sustainable development and resilience in cities	
ISO 37122:2019	Sustainable cities and communities — Indicators for smart cities	
ISO 37123:2019	Sustainable cities and communities — Indicators for resilient cities	
ISO/TR 37150:2014	Smart community infrastructures — Review of existing activities relevant to metrics	ISO/TC 268/SC1
ISO/TR 6030:2022	Smart community infrastructures – Disaster risk reduction – Survey results and gap analysis	
ISO/TS 37151:2015	Smart community infrastructures — Principles and requirements for performance metrics	
ISO/TR 37152:2016	Smart community infrastructures — Common framework for development and operation	
ISO 37153:2017	Smart community infrastructures — Maturity model for assessment and improvement	
ISO 37155-1:2020	Framework for integration and operation of smart community infrastructures — Part 1: Recommendations for considering opportunities and challenges from interactions in smart community infrastructures from relevant aspects through the life cycle	
ISO 37155-2:2021	Framework for integration and operation of smart community infrastructures — Part 2: Holistic approach and the strategy for development, operation and maintenance of smart community infrastructures	
ISO 37156:2020	Smart community infrastructures — Guidelines on data exchange and sharing for smart community infrastructures	

Document No.	Title	TC
ISO 37160:2020	Smart community infrastructure — Electric power infrastructure — Measurement methods for the quality of thermal power infrastructure and requirements for plant operations and management	
ISO 37166:2022	Smart community infrastructures — Urban data integration framework for smart city planning (SCP)	
ISO 37170:2022	Smart community infrastructures — Data framework for infrastructure governance based on digital technology in smart cities	
ISO/TS 37172:2022	Smart community infrastructures — Data exchange and sharing for community infrastructures based on geographic information	
ISO/TR 37171:2020	Report of pilot testing on the application of ISO smart community infrastructures standards	
ISO 37154:2017	Smart community infrastructures — Best practice guidelines for transportation	ISO/TC 268/SC2
ISO 37157:2018	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation for compact cities	
ISO 37158:2019	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation using battery-powered buses for passenger services	
ISO 37159:2019	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation for rapid transit in and between large city zones and their surrounding areas	
ISO 37161:2020	Smart community infrastructures — Guidance on smart transportation for energy saving in transportation services	
ISO 37162:2020	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation for newly developing areas	
ISO 37163:2020	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation for parking lot allocation in cities	
ISO 37164:2021	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation using fuel cell light rail transit (FC-LRT)	
ISO 37165:2020	Smart community infrastructures — Guidance on smart transportation with the use of digitally processed payment (d-payment)	

Document No.	Title	TC
ISO 37167:2021	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation for energy saving operation by intentionally driving slowly	
ISO 37168:2022	Smart community infrastructures — Guidance on smart transportation by Electric, Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (eCAVs) and its application to on-demand responsive passenger services with shared vehicles	
ISO 37169:2021	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation by run-through train/bus operation in/between cities	
ISO 37181:2022	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation by autonomous vehicles on public roads	
ISO 37182:2022	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation for fuel efficiency and pollution emission reduction in bus transportation services	
ISO 37184:2023	Sustainable mobility and transportation — Framework for transportation services by providing meshes for 5G communication	
ISO 37180:2021	Smart community infrastructures — Guidance on smart transportation with QR code identification and authentication in transportation and its related or additional services	

Table 9: Published standards from ISO/TC 268.

Document No.	Title	TC
ISO/CD 37111	Sustainable cities and communities – Urban districts, towns, counties and neighbourhoods – Guidelines for flexible approaches to phased implementation of ISO 37101	ISO/TC 268
ISO/CD TR 37112	Sustainable cities and communities — Good practice case studies in how smart city operating models support effective public-health emergency response	
ISO/CD 37113	Sustainable Cities and Communities — Management guidelines for public health emergency response in smart city operating models	
ISO/WD 37124	Sustainable cities and communities — Guidance on the use of ISO 37120 series of standards for cities — ISO 37120, ISO 37122 and ISO 37123	

Document No.	Title	TC
ISO/CD 37125	Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Indicators for Cities	
IEC/AWI 63205	Smart Cities Reference Architecture (SCRA)	
ISO/CD 37151	Smart community infrastructures — Principles and requirements for performance metrics	ISO/TC 268/SC1
ISO/CD 37153	Smart community infrastructures — Maturity model for assessment and improvement	
ISO/CD 37173	Smart city infrastructure — Development guidelines for information-based system of smart building	
ISO/DIS 37174	Smart community infrastructures — Disaster risk reduction — Guidelines for implementing seismometer systems	
ISO/CD 37175	Smart community infrastructures — Operation and maintenance of utility tunnels	
ISO/CD 37176	Smart community infrastructure — Responsiveness assessment and maturity model	
ISO/DTR 37178	Smart community infrastructures — Data exchange and sharing for lamppost network in smart community	
ISO/CD 37179	Smart community infrastructures — Disaster risk reduction — Basic framework for the implementation of disaster risk reduction	
ISO/DIS 37183	Smart community infrastructures — Smart transportation with the use of face recognition payment (f-payment)	ISO/TC 268/SC2

Table 10: Standards under development from ISO/TC 268.

ITU published 34 of the standards included in the dashboard. ITU is the United Nations specialized agency for information and communication technologies. Independently from the UN, it was founded in 1865 to facilitate international connectivity in communication networks. Among the allocation of global radio spectrum and satellite orbits, it develops technical standards that ensure that networks and technologies interconnect.³⁰ The mentioned standards

³⁰ <https://www.itu.int/en/about/Pages/default.aspx>

were developed within the ITU-T (ITU Telecommunication Standardizing Sector) which deals with standards which are critical to the interoperability of ICT's.³¹

Within the **ISO/TC 292 - Security and resilience** 18 of the standards with relation to PROBONO were developed. This TC was created in 2014 with the scope at standardization in the field of security to enhance the safety and resilience of society. This does not include sector specific security projects developed in other relevant ISO committees and projects developed in ISO/TC 262 and ISO/PC 278. From this TC 50 ISO standards were published whereas 17 are under development. This TC includes 14 working groups and amongst them are: ISO/TC 292/WG 2 - *Continuity and organizational resilience*, ISO/TC 292/WG 3 - *Emergency management* and ISO/TC 292/WG 5 - *Community resilience*.³²

The **ISO/TC 22 – Road vehicles** published 13 of the standards included in the PROBONO dashboard. This TC was founded in 1947 and deals with all questions of standardization concerning compatibility, interchangeability and safety, with particular reference to terminology and test procedures (including the characteristics of instrumentation) for evaluating the performance of road vehicles and their equipment as defined in the relevant items of Article 1 of the convention on Road Traffic, Vienna in 1968 concluded under the auspices of the United Nations. From this TC 992 ISO standards were published whereas 222 are under development. It is structured in 11 sub committees and 4 working groups.³³

Further 13 standards were published by **ISO/TC 59 - Buildings and civil engineering works**. The creation of this TC took place in 1947 with the aim to develop standards in the field of buildings and civil engineering works. This includes general terminology; organization of information in the processes of design, manufacture and construction; general geometric requirements for buildings, building elements and components including modular coordination and its basic principles, general rules for joints, tolerances and fits, performance and test standards for sealants; general rules for other performance requirements, including functional and user requirements related to service life, sustainability, accessibility and usability; general rules and guidelines for addressing the economic, environmental and social impacts and aspects related to sustainable development; geometric and performance requirements for components that are not in the scope of separate ISO technical committees; procurement processes, methods and

³¹ <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/about/Pages/default.aspx>

³² <https://www.iso.org/committee/5259148.html>

³³ <https://www.iso.org/committee/46706.html>

procedures. Altogether 135 ISO standards were published by this TC and 20 are still under development. It consists of 9 sub committees and 2 working groups. The subcommittees which could be most important for PROBONO are ISO/TC 59/SC 13 - *Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM)* and ISO/TC 59/SC 17 - *Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works*. Further, there is also ISO/TC 59/WG 4 - *Resilience of buildings and civil engineering works* which could be of interest for the project.³⁴ The focus of ISO/TC 59/SC 13 is on international standardization of information through the whole life cycle of buildings and infrastructure across the built environment to enable interoperability of information; to deliver a structured set of standards, specifications and reports to define, describe, exchange, monitor, record and securely handle information, semantics and processes, with links to geospatial and other related built environment information and to enable object-related digital information exchange.³⁵ The scope of ISO/TC 59/SC 17 is the standardization in the field of sustainability of new and existing construction works in the context of the UN Sustainable Development Goals and climate change mitigation and adaptation. The environmental, economic, and social aspects of sustainability and circular economy are included as appropriate.³⁶

12 standards were developed by **IEC/TC 69 - Electrical power/energy transfer systems for electrically propelled road vehicles and industrial trucks**. The scope of this TC is to prepare publications on electrical power/energy transfer systems for electrically propelled road vehicles and industrial trucks drawing current from a rechargeable energy storage system (RESS). Possibilities to transfer power/energy include conductive power/energy transfer, wireless power/energy transfer and battery swap.³⁷ This TC published already 30 standards whereas 39 are under development.

4.3 Standardization activities on European level

The main technical committees, which are responsible for the 138 European standards related to PROBONO and included in the standardization dashboard are listed in Table 11 and are

³⁴ <https://www.iso.org/committee/49070.html>

³⁵ <https://www.iso.org/committee/49180.html>

³⁶ <https://www.iso.org/committee/322621.html>

³⁷ https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:7:7116792433479:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1255,25

described in the following. In this section only the committees are considered where 5 or more standards are included in the dashboard.

CLC/TC 79	Alarm systems
ETSI	Technical Committee Smart Machine-to-Machine Communications
CEN/TC 442	Building Information Modelling (BIM)
CEN/TC 350	Sustainability of construction works
CLC/TC 69X	Electrical systems for electric road vehicles
CEN/CLC/JTC 10	Material efficiency aspects for products in scope of Ecodesign legislation
CLC/TC 210	Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC)
CLC/TC 21X	Secondary cells and batteries
CLC/TC 23H	Plugs, Socket-outlets and Couplers for industrial and similar applications, and for Electric Vehicles

Table 11: Relevant TC's on European level.

The European Standards Organisation **ETSI** (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) deals with standardization in the fields of telecommunication, broadcasting, and other electronic communication networks and services.³⁸ Regarding standards with relation to PROBONO on European level, 40 standards, were published by ETSI. The majority of those standards was published by *ETSI/SmartM2M - Technical Committee Smart Machine-to-Machine Communications*. This committee is developing standards to enable Machine-to-Machine (M2M) services and applications and certain aspects of the Internet of Things (IoT). This is also the first group in ETSI to develop Smart Cities requirements.³⁹

In the dashboard 13 standards are listed which were developed by **CEN/TC 79 – Alarm systems**. The scope of this TC is to prepare harmonized standards for detection, alarm and monitoring systems for protection of persons and property, and for elements used in these systems. The scope includes in particular intruder and hold-up alarm systems, access control systems, periphery protection systems, combined alarm - fire alarm systems, social alarm systems, CCTV-

³⁸ <https://www.etsi.org/about>

³⁹ <https://www.etsi.org/committee/smartm2m>

systems, other monitoring and surveillance systems related to security applications, as well as associated and dedicated transmission and communication systems. The standards shall specify conformity tests.⁴⁰

From **CEN/TC 442 - Building Information Modelling (BIM)** originated 10 standards from the dashboard. The TC aims to develop standards in the field of structured semantic life-cycle information for the built environment. The committee will develop a structured set of standards, specifications and reports which specify methodologies to define, describe, exchange, monitor, record and securely handle asset data, semantics and processes with links to geospatial and other external data.⁴¹ This TC has 10 working groups including CEN/TC 442/WG 9 - Digital twins in built environment which focuses on Standardization in the field of structured information for the digital twins applied to the built environment, considering methodologies and formats to define, describe, exchange, monitor, record and securely handle digital twin's data and its related processes in relation with AECOO (Architecture, Engineering, Construction, Operation & Ownership).⁴²

9 of the standards from the dashboard were published by **CEN/TC 350 - Sustainability of construction works**. This TC is responsible for the development of horizontal standardized methods for the assessment of the sustainability aspects of new and existing construction works (buildings and civil engineering works) in the context of the UN Sustainable Development Goals and of the circular economy. The methodological basis will be developed in the context of current needs, European strategies, such as mitigation, adaptation and resilience to climate change, and life cycle thinking. The standards describe coherent methodologies for the assessment of sustainability of construction works covering the assessment of environmental, social and economic performance (aspect and impacts) of buildings and civil engineering works, and the provision of construction product environmental information (EPD). It is structured in 1 subcommittee (CEN/TC 350/SC 1 - *Circular Economy in the Construction Sector*) and 6 working groups. Amongst them are CEN/TC 350/WG 1 - *Environmental performance of buildings*, CEN/TC 350/WG 5 - *Social performance assessment of building* and CEN/TC 350/WG 8 - *Sustainable refurbishment*.⁴³ The scope of CEN/TC 350/SC 1 is Standardization in the field of circular

⁴⁰ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=305:7:1370793619186501:::FSP_ORG_ID:1257171

⁴¹ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:1991542&cs=100E563A3950D53807585F6A443ACB202

⁴² https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:3106339&cs=117003A1A52A114CEEE223DD2004335D7

⁴³ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:481830&cs=1F34565A9E5B582575682802C33AE3275

economy in the built environment specifying circular principles and guidelines and requirements to facilitate the transition to a more sustainable circular economy including tools and processes to achieve this; covering design to de-construction and end-of-life scenarios in all stages of current and subsequent life cycles. This applies to new and existing construction works (buildings and civil engineering works), including their products, materials and components. The Subcommittee deals both with technical issues on circularity, as well as environmental, economic and social challenges. This work will take into account standards of CEN/TC 350 and consider the work of existing committees on subjects that may support the circular economy in the construction sector, such as ISO/TC 323 and CEN-CLC/JTC 10, including initiatives of the European Commission.⁴⁴ CEN/TC 350 already published 13 standards⁴⁵ (Table 12) and 7 are currently under development⁴⁶ (Table 13).

Document number	Title
CEN/TR 15941:2010	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Methodology for selection and use of generic data
CEN/TR 16970:2016	Sustainability of construction works - Guidance for the implementation of EN 15804
CEN/TR 17005:2016	Sustainability of construction works - Additional environmental impact categories and indicators - Background information and possibilities - Evaluation of the possibility of adding environmental impact categories and related indicators and calculation methods for the assessment of the environmental performance of buildings
EN 15643:2021	Sustainability of construction works - Framework for assessment of buildings and civil engineering works
EN 15804:2012+A2:2019	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products
EN 15804:2012+A2:2019/AC:2021	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction

⁴⁴ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2868394&cs=1E483B462A3001B254B70E3969CA6730E

⁴⁵ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:32:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:481830,25&cs=118C39840693FD1A16B425079D79D8721

⁴⁶ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:481830,25&cs=118C39840693FD1A16B425079D79D8721

Document number	Title
	products
EN 15942:2021	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Communication format business-to-business
EN 15978:2011 (Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of environmental performance of buildings - Calculation method
EN 16309:2014+A1:2014	Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of social performance of buildings - Calculation methodology
EN 16627:2015	Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of economic performance of buildings - Calculation methods
EN 17472:2022	Sustainability of construction works - Sustainability assessment of civil engineering works - Calculation methods
EN 17672:2022	Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Horizontal rules for business-to-consumer communication
EN ISO 22057:2022	Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works - Data templates for the use of environmental product declarations (EPDs) for construction products in building information modelling (BIM) (ISO 22057:2022)

Table 12: Published standards from CEN/TC 350.

Document number	Title
FprEN 17680	Sustainability of construction works - Evaluation of the potential for sustainable refurbishment of buildings
prEN 15941	Sustainability of construction works - Data quality for environmental assessment of products and construction work - Selection and use of data
prEN 15978-1	Sustainability of construction works - Methodology for the assessment of performance of buildings - Part 1: Environmental Performance
prEN 15978-2	Sustainability of construction works - Methodology for the assessment of buildings - Part 2: Social performance
WI=00350038	Connection between the contributions of CEW to sustainability and achievement of the SDGs
WI=00350039	Circular economy in the construction sector – Framework, principles, and definitions

Document number	Title
WI=00350040	Circular economy in the construction sector – Gap analysis, conclusions, and recommendations

Table 13: Standards under development from CEN/TC 350.

The **CLC/TC 69X - Electrical systems for electric road vehicles** published 9 standards from the dashboard. Their scope is to prepare European standards related to electrical systems for road vehicles, totally or partly propelled from self-contained power sources.⁴⁷

The following TCs each developed 5 of the standards included in the dashboard:

The scope of **CEN/CLC/JTC 10 - Material efficiency aspects for products in scope of Ecodesign legislation** is to consider Material efficiency aspects for products in scope of the Ecodesign Directive 2009/125/EC and its future revisions. Producing generic and horizontal CEN-CENELEC publications covering aspects such as assessment methods, design rules, dematerialization, digitalization and transfer of information on a variety of material efficiency topics, in particular (but not limited to): extending product lifetime; ability to reuse components or recycle materials from products at End-of-Life; use of reused components and/or recycled materials in products.⁴⁸

CLC/TC 210 - Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) aims to prepare EMC standards and guidelines with particular emphasis on the application of the EMC Directive and other EC Directives that contain EMC references and to coordinate all EMC activities in CENELEC.⁴⁹

The scope of **CLC/TC 21X - Secondary cells and batteries** is to execute the following standardization activities for secondary cells and batteries: to implement IEC/TC 21/SC 21A documents into CENELEC standards; to prepare Product Standards, general requirements and methods of testing included to prepare Safety Standards and associated Codes of Practice and to consider Environmental Requirements (EC Rules) for the products.⁵⁰

To prepare standards for industrial plugs, socket-outlets and couplers suitable for use in industrial, commercial, private or public locations, either indoors or outdoors **CLC/TC 23H - Plugs, Socket-outlets and Couplers for industrial and similar applications, and for Electric Vehicles** was created. It further aims to prepare standards for other accessories, such as

⁴⁷ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=305:7:0:25:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1258145

⁴⁸ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2240017&cs=18A65BEA4289B745403E9407952618CE3

⁴⁹ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=305:7:0:25:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1258289

⁵⁰ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=305:7:0:25:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1257217

industrial cable reels among others, intended for use with industrial plugs, socket-outlets and couplers. In addition, standards for connection products intended for the connection of electric vehicles to the supply network and/or to dedicated supply equipment are developed. The rated voltages of products covered by these standards lie within IEC 60038.⁵¹

⁵¹ https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=305:7:0:25:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2054077

4.4 Standards related to PROBONO

4.4.1 General

Figure 11 from the ISO brochure “ISO and sustainable cities”⁵² from 2020 shows which areas and therefore TC’s on international level are connected to the big topic of sustainable cities. This illustrates why it is important within the PROBONO project to evaluate which areas are important for the consortium to look at for existing standards.

Figure 11: TC’s on international level related to sustainable cities (extracted from the ISO brochure “ISO and sustainable cities”).⁵²

With the workshop and the standardization session, areas were defined for which an overview of the standardization landscape could be useful for the work of all WP’s within PROBONO. In the following subclauses those areas are examined with regard to the relevant TC’s and standards in those areas.

4.4.2 Green Building Neighbourhoods

Since one big topic within the PROBONO project is to define the GBN frameworks for the project, the standards published from ISO/TC 268 are of high importance for the project work. Therefore, the published standards from this TC as well as the standards under development are listed in Table 9 and Table 10. Due to the high relevance of the standards series “Sustainable cities and communities” (ISO 37100 – ISO 37123) these documents were provided for the partners to work with. The flagship standard of ISO/TC 268 is, as ISO promotes on their website, ISO 37101 *Sustainable development in communities – Management system for sustainable development – Requirements with guidance for use*.⁵³ It is aimed at city leaders and shall provide an overall

⁵² <https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/store/en/PUB100423.pdf>

⁵³ <https://www.iso.org/sdg/SDG11.html>

framework of what a sustainable community is and how to achieve one. The standard presents a guideline on what a city shall address to become smarter, such as responsible resource use, environmental management, citizens' health and well-being, governance, mobility and more. This standard is supported by a number of different standards in areas such as terminology and key indicators for measuring the performance of city services (Table 9). Within the PROBONO project those "Sustainable cities and communities"-standards will be used to establish a common GBN-framework. Those standards provide a comprehensive and well-structured framework for sustainable development in communities. This framework can guide the design, implementation and evaluation of the different WP's within PROBONO to ensure that they all contribute to the overall objectives of the project. It creates a common vocabulary and set of principles for sustainable development in communities. By using the same terminology and concepts, the different WP's can communicate more effectively and ensure that their efforts are coordinated and aligned. In addition, those standards will be used to define and also quantify GBNs since ISO 37100 provides a vocabulary and set of principles for sustainable development in communities. These include definitions, concepts and terminology that can be used to create a common understanding of what constitutes a green building neighbourhood. ISO 37120, focuses on indicators for urban services and quality of life. This standard can be used to measure and benchmark the performance of GBNs in terms of sustainability. These indicators can help to monitor progress, evaluate the effectiveness of policies and measures, and identify areas for improvement. To deliver actionable inputs ISO 37101 provides guidance on sustainable development in communities, including the establishment of a sustainable development management system. This can be used to plan, implement and review actions to improve GBN sustainability. The standard encourages stakeholder engagement, setting goals and targets, monitoring and evaluating performance, and promoting continuous improvement. The ISO 37100 family of standards, in particular ISO 37101, provides guidance for implementing a sustainable development management system in communities. This includes the processes for planning, implementing, monitoring and reviewing actions to improve sustainability. By applying the same methodology across all WP's, the project teams can ensure that their efforts are consistent and complementary and that way develop harmonized methodologies.

4.4.3 Digital solutions

4.4.3.1 Building Information Management (BIM)

To develop standards with regard to BIM on European level CEN/TC 442 – *Building Information Modelling* exists whereas on international level those topics are not dealt within a specific TC but within a SC in ISO/TC 59 - *Buildings and civil engineering works*. One standard series which is important in the field of BIM is ISO 19650 - *Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) - Information management using building information modelling*. Another series of standards (ISO 19650) focuses on *Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) - Information management using building information modelling*. Since there are a lot of standards already existing with connection to BIM in the PROBONO dashboard only those were included which are related to the given keywords.

4.4.3.2 Digital Twin and Internet of Things (IoT)

The field of digital twins and IoT is covered by a broad range of standards within a lot TC's on international and European level. A large amount of those standards is developed by ITU-T. For IoT there are e.g., ITU-T X.1369 *Security requirements for IoT service platform* or ITU-T Y.4100 *Common requirements of the Internet of things*. With regard to digital twins e.g., ITU-T Y.3090 *Digital twin network - Requirements and architecture* and ITU-T Y.4600 *Requirements and capabilities of a digital twin system for smart cities* were published. The topics related to IoT and digital twins are covered on ISO-level by ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 - *Internet of things and digital twin*. This TC published documents like ISO/IEC 20924 *Internet of Things (IoT) and Digital Twin – Vocabulary*, ISO/IEC TR 30172 *Digital Twin - Use cases*, ISO/IEC 30141 *Internet of Things (IoT) - Reference Architecture* or ISO/IEC 30179 *Internet of Things (IoT) - Overview and general requirements of IoT system for ecological environment monitoring*.

4.4.3.3 Data and Information Management

The topic data and information management can cover a wide range of subtopics. Therefore, the focus was laid to integrate those standards in the PROBONO dashboard which could be found by using the keywords required that they were not too vague. Besides ITU-T relevant TC's are also ISO/IEC JTC 1, ISO/TC 171 *Document management applications*, ISO/TC 154 *Processes, data elements and documents in commerce, industry and administration* or ISO/TC 307

Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies. Interesting standards for project partners could for example be ISO/IEC 11002 *Information technology - Multipath management (API)*, ITU-T Y.4561 *Blockchain-based data management for supporting Internet of things and smart cities and communities* or ISO 37156 *Smart community infrastructures - Guidelines on data exchange and sharing for smart community infrastructures*.

4.4.3.4 Dual Distributed Network (DDN)

There were no standards found that explicitly addressed DDN.

4.4.4 Materials

The topic Materials has from one point of view a quite strong connection to the topic Buildings which is why the focus of the first part of this subclause lays on this subarea. One very important TC in this area is CEN/TC 350 *Sustainability of construction works* which published several standards with the main topic *Sustainability of construction* like EN 15804 *Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products* or CEN/TR 15941 *Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Methodology for selection and use of generic data*. Within ISO/TC 71 *Concrete, reinforced concrete and pre-stressed concrete* the standards series ISO 13315 was developed which focuses on *Environmental management for concrete and concrete structures*. Standards with regard to *Environmental labels and declarations* (ISO 14021 - 14027) were published by ISO/TC 207 *Environmental management*. From the CEN/CLC/JTC 10 *Energy-related products - Material efficiency aspects for ecodesign* several for PROBONO possibly relevant standards were published like EN 45557 *General method for assessing the proportion of recycled material content in energy-related products* or EN 45558 *General method to declare the use of critical raw materials in energy-related products*.

4.4.5 Mobility

The topic of mobility can also cover a wide range within the context of PROBONO. Within ISO/TC 268 *Sustainable cities and communities* a series of standards with regard to *Smart community infrastructures* was published (ISO/TR 6030, ISO/TS 37151, ISO/TR 37152 and ISO 37150 – 37182) which examines the topic from different angles. Another relevant international TC in the area of Mobility is ISO/TC 204 *Intelligent transport systems* or IEC/TC 69 *Electric road vehicles and electric industrial trucks*. On European level, the following TC's exist in this area: CEN/TC 278 *Intelligent transport systems* and CEN/TC 320 *Transport - Logistics and services*.

When focussing in this context on electric vehicle charging, the following TC's and standards could be of high importance for PROBONO:

Within IEC/TC 69 *Electric road vehicles and electric industrial trucks* amongst others the IEC 61851-series to *Electric vehicle conductive charging systems*, the IEC 62840-series to *Electrical vehicle battery swap systems* and IEC 61980-series to *Electric vehicle wireless power transfer (WPT)* were developed. IEC/SC 23H *Industrial plugs and socket-outlets* published the IEC 62196-series with the topic of *Plugs, socket-outlets, vehicle connectors and vehicle inlets - Conductive charging of electric vehicles*. The ISO 15118-series with the topic *Road vehicles - Vehicle to grid communication interface* was developed within ISO/TC 22 *Road vehicles*.

4.4.6 Energy

ISO alone has already published more than 200 standards which are directly related to energy efficiency and renewables.⁵² Relevant TC's on international level are e.g., ISO/TC 163 *Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment*, ISO/TC 180 *Solar Energy* and ISO/TC 301 *Energy management and energy savings*. On European level the following TC's could be relevant in the context of PROBONO: CEN/CLC/JTC 14 *Energy management and energy efficiency in the framework of energy transition*, CEN/SS F23 *Energy* and CEN/TC 371 *Energy performance of buildings*. The standards included in the PROBONO dashboard cover amongst other the topics of Energy performance of buildings (e.g., EN 15459-1 *Energy performance of buildings - Economic evaluation procedure for energy systems in buildings - Part 1: Calculation procedures, Module M1-14*), Energy efficiency (e.g., ISO 17742 *Energy efficiency and savings calculation for countries, regions and cities*, EN ISO/IEC 13273-1 *Energy efficiency and renewable energy sources - Common international terminology - Part 1: Energy efficiency (ISO/IEC 13273-1:2015)*; ISO/IEC 13273-series *Energy efficiency and renewable energy sources - Common international terminology*) or Energy management (e.g., ISO/TS 50008 *Energy management and energy savings - Building energy data management for energy performance - Guidance for a systemic data exchange approach*). The ISO 52000 series contains a comprehensive method for assessing the energy performance of building whereas the standard ISO 50001 provides a strategic tool to help organisations put in place an energy management system for more efficient energy use. To measure the energy performance ISO 50006 gives guidance on how to establish, use and maintain energy performance indicators and energy baselines. On *Energy management systems* a whole series of standards exist (ISO 50001 – ISO 50015).

4.4.7 Accessibility

The topic of accessibility is covering in the world of standards a wide range of different areas. That is the reason why different European TC's are dealing with "accessibility" in various variants: CEN/CLC/ETSI/JWG eAcc – *eAccessibility*, CEN/CLC/JTC 11 - *Accessibility in the built environment* or CEN/TC 293 - *Assistive products and accessibility*. Within the context of PROBONO there are several standards which could be important like those within the area of *Ergonomics of human-system interactions* (ISO 9241 series) or ICT products (e.g., EN 301549 *Accessibility requirements for ICT products and services*). Further, there are also the ones which are dealing with *accessibility and usability of the built environment* (e.g., EN 17210 *Accessibility and usability of the built environment - Functional requirements*). One standard which is also worth mentioning in the PROBONO context is EN 17161 *Design for All - Accessibility following a Design for All approach in products, goods and services - Extending the range of users*. Due to the wide range of standards within this topic only the ones which were found by using the keywords were added to the PROBONO dashboard.

4.4.8 Resilience

The relevant TC regarding the topic of resilience and also security is ISO/TC 292 - *Security and resilience*. This TC published a series of standards with the main topic "security and resilience" as well as about "societal security". Not all of the 50 published standards were added to the PROBONO standards dashboard but only the ones which were found by using the keywords since those are the important ones for the consortium. Only a selection of the standards covering the topic of "security and resilience" were added to the dashboard amongst others those which are dealing with "Community resilience".

But there are also important other standards which could be of high importance for PROBONO but were published by other TCs. Definitions and methodologies for a set of indicators on resilient cities are established by ISO 37123:2019 *Sustainable cities and communities – Indicators for resilient cities*.⁵⁴ Further, there are some specifications which could be quite interesting for PROBONO like ISO/TR 37121:2017 *Sustainable development in communities – Inventory of existing guidelines and approaches on sustainable development and resilience in cities* or several CWA's on *City Resilience Development* (CWA 17300 – 17302, CWA 17727).

⁵⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/70428.html>

5 Conclusion and next steps

Generally, the present deliverable gives an overview of the standardization landscape related to the PROBONO project and therefore summarizes the results of subtask ST9.4.1 – *Investigate relevant standards*. The knowledge about existing standards is important for the project since it enables the development of solutions which are compliant with the latest standards and further paves the way for upcoming liaison activities with relevant technical committees. Therefore, a standards database in form of a dashboard was created which includes 482 standards which could be relevant for the project. On one hand, this dashboard offers the opportunity to search for specific standards. On the other hand, the overview of this dashboard provides the opportunity to identify standardization gaps and is therefore the basis for the following subtasks ST9.4.2 – *Develop standardization strategy* and ST9.4.3 – *Performing standardization activities* (Figure 12). Within this deliverable, the dashboard was used to describe the standardization activities on international and European level related to PROBONO. A specific focus was put on particular areas which have a high relevance for the project. Besides listing relevant standards, this deliverable offers an overview of the TC's that are working on standards related to PROBONO. Since the interaction with relevant standardization committees is targeted in ST9.4.3, an overview of current work items of the most relevant TC's is provided. In this context it is also worth mentioning the importance to really focus on specific areas within a broad field like GBN's. The next steps include further focusing of the areas to initiate targeted standardization activities within PROBONO. In particular, an individual exchange with PROBONO's Living Labs is sought. Within ST9.4.2 the contribution to ongoing or the initiation of new standardization activities is sought. Within a workshop the standardization needs and therefore the existence of possible standardization gaps within the project will be analysed. This will then directly result in ST9.4.3, the performance of standardization activities. Altogether, through the work done within ST9.4.1 the awareness for standardization was raised throughout the consortium and the basis was laid for the subsequent subtasks.

Figure 12: Overview of the subtasks of Task 9.4 – Standardization activities.

Annexes

A.1 - Survey on Standardization

Survey on Standardization

Dear PROBONO partners,

standardization can offer a great opportunity in R&I projects. Maybe some of you already got in contact with standardization while others might not. Therefore, we would like to gain some insight into how much you already know about standardization and what your expectations are.

In order to use the impact of standardization within PROBONO to its fullest, we kindly ask you to participate in our short survey. It will only take 5 min of your time. We want to use this as a first step to get in touch with you and get to know you.

Should you have any questions, doubts, or comments that do not fit in this questionnaire, please contact Madlen Schmutde (madlen.schmutde@din.de).

Thank you for your time!

Best wishes,
Madlen

Personal Information

This information will help us to contact you and provide further information.

1. Name *

Meine Antwort _____

2. Partner Affiliation *

Meine Antwort _____

3. In which workpackages in PROBONO will you be mainly active? *

- WP1
- WP2
- WP3
- WP4
- WP5
- WP6
- WP7
- WP8
- WP9
- WP10

Standardization

Standardization is a key strategic tool that can be used to define product, process and service requirements as well as guidelines. In the standardization system technical experts agree for example on standardized terminology, methodologies, and quality criteria. A standard is a document, established by a consensus of all interested stakeholders. It should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology and experience, with the aim to promote the optimum community benefits.

4. Are you applying / planing to apply standards within your activities in the PROBONO project?

Yes

No

If yes, please let us know which one(s) / in which area.

Meine Antwort _____

5. Do you need an overview of the available standards for a specific area within PROBONO?

- Yes
 No

If yes, for which area(s)?

Meine Antwort _____

6. Is there anything you would like to standardize? Or are you aware of an area in the context of PROBONO where standards are still missing?

- Yes
 No

If yes, please let us know.

Meine Antwort _____

7. Have you ever been / are you currently active in a standardization committee (Technical Committee)?

- Yes
 No

If yes, which one(s)? Please explain very shortly.

Meine Antwort _____

8. Have you ever developed a pre-standardization document like e.g. CWA?

- Yes
 No

If yes, please explain very shortly.

Meine Antwort _____

9. Do you have any expectation for the PROBONO standardization activities?

Yes

No

If yes, which ones?

Meine Antwort _____

A.2 Presentation standardization session at GA on 22nd February 2023

The Integrator -centric approach for realizing innovative energy efficient buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods

Standardisation Session

Task 9.4 – Standardisation Activities

Dr. Madlen Schmudde
DIN
General Assembly Meeting, Chania, Greece
22th February 2023

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Agenda

WP9

- I. Main facts about standardization
- II. Standardisationlandscape for GBN
- III. StandardisationWorkshop
 - I. Needs for an overview of the standardization landscape
 - II. Collection of Keywords for the standards research
 - III. Which standards are already used within PROBONO?
 - IV. Do you already see standardization needs?
 - V. Next steps

Challenges

WP9

Have you ever faced the challenge...

- of explaining something to a person who didn't understand you;
- of missing a network for mutual support or the exchange of ideas;
- that the solutions you developed were not compatible with the existing ones?

Main benefits of standardisation

WP9

Standards...

PROBONO

What is the difference between standards and IPR?

WP9

IPR – Intellectual Property Rights

What is the difference between standards and IPR?

WP9

IPR – Intellectual Property Rights
FRAND – Fair, Reasonable And Non-Discriminatory

What is standardisation and what is a standard?

WP9

Standardisation...

activity of establishing, with regards to actual or potential problems, provisions for common and repeatable use, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context.

(Source: EN 45020:2006 Standardization and related activities - General vocabulary (ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004))

Standard...

document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context

(Source: EN 45020:2006 Standardization and related activities - General vocabulary (ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004))

Standards from my everyday life...

WP9

Paper size...

- Everyone knows DIN A4– 21.0 x 29.7 cm
- Reason why the paper fits in every printer, folder,...
- 1922 published as the German standard DIN 476
- Today it is internationally recognized: DIN EN ISO 216 Writing paper and certain classes of printed matter- Trimmed sizes - A and B series, and indication of machine direction

Deutsche Industrie-Normen		Papierformate				476
Formel	Reihe A	Reihe B	Reihe C	Reihe D		
0	1000	1414	2000	2828		
1	707	1000	1414	2000		
2	500	707	1000	1414		
3	354	500	707	1000		
4	250	354	500	707		
5	178	250	354	500		
6	125	178	250	354		
7	88	125	178	250		
8	63	88	125	178		
9	45	63	88	125		
10	32	45	63	88		
11	23	32	45	63		
12	16	23	32	45		
13	11	16	23	32		

Main characteristics of standards

WP9

Standard...

consensus based document that is approved by a recognized body with the following characteristics :

- should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology and experience;
- provides rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results;
- developed by all interested stakeholders;
- recognized by a standardisation body;
- reflects the state-of-the-art.

Who develops standards?

WP9

Who is DIN?

WP9

DIN -German Institute for Standardization

- Responsible German standards body
- Non-profit association
- > 500 employees
- > 3,400 members and ≈ 36,000 experts
- ≈ 34,800 DIN standards
- 69 DIN Technical Committees
- Member of ISO and CEN

Who develops standards?

WP9

How are standards developed?

WP9

How are the committees structured?

WP9

Have you ever been / are you currently active in a standardization committee (Technical Committee)?

If yes, please write the following information on a note:

- Your full name
- Your company
- The standardization committee

Results from standardisation

The deliverable of the standardisation process is a document...
which provides *rules, guidelines or characteristics* for activities or their results.

Types of standardisation deliverables

WP9

What standardisation deliverables will we develop within PROBONO? WP9

Specification...

document agreed upon by the group of developers, which is designed to meet an immediate need and form the basis for future standardisation activities.

- developed outside the technical committee structure
- open to the direct participation of anyone
- offers rapid development opportunities (6 – 12 month)
- publication within duration of project is possible

What is the benefit of engaging in standardisation for PROBONO? WP9

What is our task within PROBONO? WP9

Help consortium members to consider and use existing standards. Form the basis for the identification of gaps in the existing standards repository in the field of PROBONO.

Standards research

In which specific area do you need an overview of the standardisation landscape?

Overview of standards and Technical Committees → your basis to work with

Standardisation Potentials

Do you miss any standards?

Can we develop a standard out of PROBONO results?

Standardisation Activities

Development of a specification

Participation in Technical Committees at CEN or ISO

What does the standardisation landscape for GBN look like? WP9

Technical Committees (TC) on international level...

ISO/TC 268

WP9

Sustainable Cities and Communities

- Since 2012
- standardization in the field of Sustainable Cities and Communities including the development of requirements, frameworks, guidance and supporting techniques and tools related to the achievement of sustainable development considering smartness and resilience
- 35 participating members
- 41 published ISO standards
- 17 ISO standards under development

ISO/TC 268

WP9

Sustainable Cities and Communities

ISO/TC 268

WP9

- ISO 37101:2016 Sustainable development in communities – Management system for sustainable development – Requirements with guidance for use
- overall framework of what a sustainable community is and how to achieve one
- guideline on what a city must address to become smarter, such as responsible resource use, environmental management, citizens’ health and well-being, governance, mobility and more
- supported by a number of different standards in areas such as terminology and key indicators for measuring the performance of city services
 - ISO 37100: Sustainable cities and communities – Vocabulary
 - ISO 37105: Sustainable cities and communities – Descriptive framework for cities and communities
 - ISO 37120: Sustainable cities and communities – Indicators for city services and quality of life

What does the standardisation landscape for GBN look like? WP9

European level...

CEN/TC 465 Sustainable Cities and Communities

- equivalent to ISO/TC 268
- Established in 2020
- Takeover of ISO 37101:2016 → EN ISO 37101:2022 Sustainable development in communities - Management system for sustainable development - Requirements with guidance for use

Sector Forum Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities (SF-SSCC)

- strategic structure between CEN-CENELEC and ETSI
- Created in 2017
- advisory and coordinating body for European standardization activities in the field of smart and sustainable cities and communities → won't develop own standards

What does the standardisation landscape for PROBONO look like? WP9

How to create a standardization landscape...

What does the standardisation landscape for PROBONO look like? WP9

Where is an overview of the standardization landscape necessary for you?

Answers from the survey...

WP 9

In which topic area is an overview of the current standards necessary for you?

Please raise your hand and let us know the generic term!

What does the standardisation landscape for PROBONO look like? WP9

Where is an overview of the standardization landscape necessary for you?

Answers from the survey...

WP 9

Which are the keywords when thinking about this topic area?

Write the keyword(s) on a note and put it at the topic area!

Note: This is to specify the topic area.

A.3 Survey after the standardization session

The image shows a mobile app interface for a survey form. At the top, the title "PROBONO - Follow-up Standardisation Session" is displayed in dark green text. Below the title, there is a small cloud icon and a three-dot menu icon. The form is titled "Personal information" and contains three required fields, each marked with an asterisk and the text "* Erforderlich". The fields are: "1. Name: *" with a text input field containing "Ihre Antwort eingeben"; "2. Organisation: *" with a text input field containing "Ihre Antwort eingeben"; and "3. E-Mail: *" with a text input field containing "Ihre Antwort eingeben". At the bottom of the form, there is a dark green button with the text "Weiter" in white.

PROBONO - Follow-up
Standardisation Session

...

* Erforderlich
Abschnitt

4. Which standards do you already use within PROBONO?
e.g. for developing the solutions, within your research...

*

Ihre Antwort eingeben

Zurück Weiter

PROBONO - Follow-up
Standardisation Session

...

* Erforderlich
Abschnitt

5. Do you already see standardization needs within the context of PROBONO?
e.g. Do you miss any standards when developing your PROBONO solution? / Do you already see the potential of any PROBONO solution to be standardised?

*

Ihre Antwort eingeben

Zurück Absenden

A.4 Topic areas, areas and keywords for the standards research

Biodiversity
Sensors to measure biodiversity
Buildings
Constructional quality
Integration batteries in buildings
Local Building Codes & Products or system requirements
Indoor environmental quality
Digital solutions
Dual Distributed Networks (DDN)
Biz (Business) Continuity
Collaboration (integrator)
Cost
Data communication
Data Direct Network
Data Management
Decentralisation
Distributed
Efficiency
Energy
Energy reduction
Interoperability
IOT surveillance
IOT/Data (SAREF - Smart Applications REference)
Lifecycle comfort
Load balancing
Monetisation
Ontology
Data Management / Information Management
(EU) Ontologies
(Open) protocols
ABM (agent-based model)
Accessibility
API (application programming interface)
Availability
Backups
Big Brother
blockchain
Cloud services
Communication protocols
Contracts
Cyber security

Data
Data analysis
Data collection
Data dissemination
Data distribution
Data driven tools
Data modelling
Data protocols
Data quality
Data sharing
Data types/formats
Databases
Dataspaces
DT
GDPR
Integration
Interoperability
IOT (Internet of Things)
ISO 19650
KG
KPIs
Latency
Legal liability
Monetisation
Monitoring
Monitoring systems
Non-proprietary
MQTT (network protocol for message queue/message queuing service.)
Open data
Operational
Personal privacy -data usage
Platforms
Privacy
Privacy & security
Readiness
Realtime
Realtime access to data
Rest (Representational state transfer)
Secure
Security
Semantic search
Sensors
Sharing

Stakeholders
Trust
Veracity
Visualisation
Building Information Management (BIM)
3D information
Accuracy
AECOO (Architecture, Engineering, Construction, Owner, Operator)
Amount model correlation to real building
CDE(Common Data Environment)
Clash detection
Collaboration
Data modelling of buildings
Data repository
Data synchronisation
Data v context
Dataspaces of buildings
Digital representation
Digital Twins
Digitalisation
Energy
Health fuel-being
Human centred integration
IFC (Industry foundation classes?)
Materials
Modelling/Simulation
Models
Object oriented
Occupants/users
Organisation & info strategy
Process
Replicability
Security
Simulation
Digital Twin / IoT architecture
Actuator
AI
AI automated systems
Anticipation
Big data
BIM
Blockchain
Building management systems

Communication protocols for scarce resources (sensors)
Connectivity
Data
Data storage
Databases
Digital Twin
Efficiency
Fault detection diagnosis
Flexibility
Mobility
Model simulation
Monitoring (systems)
Network
Predicted Maintenance
Prediction
Real time data
Realtime
Scope 3 impacts
Security
privacy
Sensors
data management
information management
Energy
Sensors to monitor energy efficiency
Accessibility
B2B
Biz Continuity
C-Infrastructure (circular?)
Collaboration (integrator)
Cost
Data management
Efficiency
Emissions
Energy community
Geothermal
Green
Integrate different products
IOT/Data (SAREF - Smart Applications REference ontology)
Mobility
Monetisation
Multiple sources
nZEB (net zero energy building)

Ontology
Operates
Profitability
Reduced energy / reduction
Renewable
RES (renewable energy systems/science/ electricity standard)
Resilience
Responsibility
Self sufficiency
Sharing (communities)
Storage
Transportation
Waste
Zero consumption
Thermal comfort
Energy reduction
Materials
Recycled raw materials
Additional "cost" if no passport/origin
Asphalt
Building products (a German thing)
Carbon calculator
Circular economy
Circular point when material reuse
Circularity
Concrete
Durability
Embodied energy
End of life-disposal-waste management
Environmental data
EPD (Environmental Product Declaration)
Functional
Life cycle assessment
Local sources
Local
Low-carbon
Material passport
National standard for used materials
Nature based solutions
Prefabricated materials
Quality
Recycled raw material
Recycling

Resilience
Responsible sourcing
Reuse
Reusability
Security
Static
Sustainability
Sustainable packing
Sustainable procurement
Thermal/physical properties
Trace from where to linked to workplace standards
Traceability (of raw materials)
Trackability
Upcycling
Upcycling of material
Methodology
Life-cycle assessment (LCA)
Mobility
Electric vehicle charging
Electric mobility
Mobility data collection
ABM (agent-based modelling)
Accessibility
Accessibility to utilities
Active transportation modes and usability
Adaption
Affordability
Air quality
Awareness
Behaviour
Charging Points
Children travel
Communication protocols for charging
Electric vehicle Charging
Energy
Energy vectors
Environment
Green
Health
Infrastructure
Licensing
M. ASA Service (Mobility as a service?)
Mobility Data collection

Monitoring personal mobility
Multi modular
Neighbour quality
Network
Public transport (- punctuality reliability)
Road safety & security
Security
Sharing
To integrate different charger technologies
Transport flow modelling
Travel behaviour change
Universal Security
V2G(Vehicle to grid)/G2V
sustainable mobility
digital twin
IoT
Others
Business models
Environment monitoring
Governance models
Outdoor air quality
Outdoor thermal comfort
Sustainable investment
Workspace conditions
Responsive
Water collection and storage
Well-being
Social quality when optimising air flow
User behaviour
User profile
Sensors to measure CCA (climate change adaptation?)
Neighbour quality
Trace from where to linked to workplace standards
Implementation of the planned innovations (mechanical, electrical local codes)
Social responsibility
Awareness
Behaviour change
Circular Economy
Collaboration + social
Communication + responsibility
Communication + social
Community + social
Community engagement

Compromise
Data protection + social
Education + social
Empowerment
Energy community
Engagement + social
Environmental accountability
Environmental quality
Equality
Equality assurance
Governance
Health protection + social / responsibility
Health/sustainable procurement
Inclusion
Investment + social
Lifestyle
Outreach
Privacy (e.g. data)
Reporting
Salary/pension
SDGs (sustainable development goals)
Trust (mis.)
Trust national -> less corruption
Welfare
Wellbeing
Accessibility
Mobility
Accessible technology
Digital Access
Disability
Disable people access to tools and buildings
Distance/accessibility to green areas
Economic
Equality
Inclusiveness
Indoor building environment
Information sharing
Interfaces
Investment
Knowledge/info availability
Micromobility
Neuro-diverse
Pedestrians

Public/private
Removing barriers
Service availability
Services
Social accessibility (e.g. Gender, social class)
Universal
Universal design
Safety
Asset Management
Assurance (insurance)
Behaviour change
Children
Climate resilience
Construction site
Crime
Cyber Security
Data protection
Emergency telecommunications
Energy hub -> Grid safety
Epidemic
Facility Management
Fire
Fire fighting
GDPR/Cyber
Hazard materials
Health
Information logistics
Infra-safety (design)
Micromobility
Mitigation plans
Mobility (EVs) & infrastructures
Oldies
Pedestrian safety
Privacy (lack of)
Protocols
Road safety (DBO - design, build and operate?)
Safe bike roads (cycle paths?)
Security data/cyber
Security people
Services
Shared mobility
Social justice
Social security

Stakeholders
Supplies
Surveillance
Tech risks
Training
Trust
Well-lit roads (street lighting?)
Resilience
Resilient communities
Buildings
Energy
Food